

DEVELOPING THE MUSICAL ABILITY OF STUDENTS IN MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS

Abdullaev Rustam Ubaydullaevich

National Center for Training Teachers
on New Methods of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

Abstract: This article describes the theoretical basis for the formation of students' musical abilities in the lessons of music culture in primary school on the basis of types of musical activities. It also provides detailed information on the types of musical activities.

Key words: music culture, elementary education, musical ability, skill, types of musical activity.

Today, fundamental socio-political changes in our country have an impact on the music education system. Solving the problem of raising a person to become a perfect person in all respects is the need of the times. At the same time, education of young people in the spirit of respect for our national musical heritage and love for the motherland are tasks that cannot be minimized. We came to the following conclusions in our graduation work on the topic of creative activities in music education and their teaching methods.

Music education can be conventionally divided into two stages. The first is the preparation stage. The main goal is to develop the student's musical skills. During this time, the student should learn to distinguish specific features of musical sounds, such as pitch and duration, and prepare to learn musical notation. At the second stage, one begins to learn musical notation, i.e. direct representation of musical sounds in a graphic way - musical notation. In the process of music training, the child perceives the reality of life through musical images.

Age-appropriate musical works leave an unforgettable impression on children and enrich their spiritual world. Musical education in kindergarten is carried out in an integral connection with fiction and visual arts. The way of chanting, listening to musical works of the genre, in particular instrumental pieces with a plot, playing musical games and dancing, music training is often defined by the artistic word. Visual art works are usefully used so that the child can vividly imagine and deeply perceive artistic images.

Each music lesson conducted using different methods arouses artistic aesthetic pleasure in children, develops their feelings, develops creative thinking and speech. In addition, musical games and postanovkas, dances develop the student's sense of rhythm, agility and mobility skills, and help the correct growth of height. Music

learning ability mainly consists of the following types of music learning: musical learning, the ability to feel the pitch and lowness of musical sounds, timbre learning (the ability to distinguish different and unique aspects of musical sounds), sense of rhythm and music. memory.

The main goals and tasks of music education can be defined as follows:

- To increase the student's interest in music and teach him to love it.
- Enriching students' imaginations about music by creating emotional feelings in the process of introducing them to musical works.
- To introduce the student to the concepts of simple music, to listen to music, to sing, to act with music, to dance, and to develop the student's ability to play tunes on simple musical instruments and develop his creative ability.

Nurturing the student's voice, forming the initial skills of singing, teaching to sing songs simply, fluently, freely, naturally and expressively.

- Being influenced by musical works, developing the student's musical taste and artistic discussion skills on this basis.
- Improvisation in the process of various music lessons, expressing the artistic image in music by means of games and choral voices, inventing a new game for a certain musical theme.

Music is an integral part of our daily life by connecting musical education activities with kindergarten life, widely using tunes and songs learned in various activities and ceremonies held in kindergarten, organizing various mornings and concerts. To make the student understand that he is a friend.

Listening to music in different groups. Being able to listen to music and enjoy it aesthetically is a great art. A person's culture of listening to music begins to develop from a young age. Listening to music in kindergarten is its foundation. The child already listens to music and perceives it during all elements of music training. But the music listening part of the training has its own serious tasks. First of all, it should be remembered that a person's ability to listen is much wider than his ability to sing. For example: works performed by an orchestra, choir, and solo instruments can only be understood by listening, not by singing. Therefore, scientists pay special attention to listening to music in the process of musical education.

Because listening to music, skills and abilities play a big role in the formation and development of a person's musical culture. When listening to music, the student's artistic perception develops well. The music listening part of the lesson is preceded by the following tasks:

- 1) Acquaint the student with samples of folk classical and modern music suitable for his perception;
- 2) Developing the student's ability to perceive music; To learn to give basic information about music, to remember the names of the works, to distinguish

between their content, character and means of expression, and to give a certain amount of artistic evaluation to the works listened to.

Music literacy - it is known that music literacy in the music lessons of general education school is different in that it consists of a complex knowledge about music. Along with the musical notation elements studied in the process of chanting, the musical literacy includes musical genres, their forms and structures, means of expression, concepts of the essence of folk and composer's music, types of performance, musical instruments and their sound timbres, etc. In the process of music education and upbringing, the musical literacy of students should be formed on the basis of this set of knowledge. It is the main component of music culture.

Listening to music - the activity of listening to music in the lesson plays a big role in enriching students' musical impressions, expanding their imagination, developing their listening skills and developing their musical taste. In this type of activity of the lesson, the students will listen to the exemplary performance of the rarest musical works performed by the music teacher, using an electrophone and a tape recorder. Choir, orchestra, ensemble and soloists perform classical works of various genres, they step into the great arena of art for the first time.

Music education includes listening to music, memorizing songs, performing various movements with music, playing musical instruments, reading books about music and musicians, attending theater, concerts, etc. 'consists of learning. Listening to happy music of elementary school students with pleasure, playing musical instruments with interest and performing songs and dances is the basis of the work carried out to educate their interest in music. Active listening to music forms performance skills in the student. Discussions after listening to music have a great educational value, the teacher creates and strengthens the spirit of mutual recognition and mutual trust between students.

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